

SOLVENT EFFECT ON THE ULTRAVIOLET ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF SULPHOXIDES. PART I

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The ultraviolet absorption spectra of several sulphoxides in both ethanol and *cyclohexane* (or *hexane*²) are recorded and an attempt has been made to explain the observed solvent effects.

The ultraviolet absorption spectra of sulphoxides have been studied, notably by Bordwell and Boutan (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 717) and Leandri *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1386). But the study cannot be said to be exhaustive. Many points of interest yet remain to be elucidated. The sulphanyl group may be assumed to resemble either the sulphonyl or the sulphide group. The comparison to the sulphonyl group can be justified from the existence of the common sulphur—oxygen bond. The comparison to the sulphide group can be justified from the existence of the 3s² lone pair of electrons. When electronic excitation occurs in a sulphoxide like methylphenyl sulphoxide, either structure (I) or (II) should contribute to the excited state. If the sulphoxide behaves like methylphenyl sulphone, excitation leads to a greater contribution of (I). If it behaves like methylphenyl sulphide, (II) is the contributing structure to the excited state. From the spectral data, recorded by Price and Hydock (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 1943) and Bordwell and Boutan (*loc. cit.*), the view that the methylsulphanyl group enters into electron-donor type of conjugation in the photo-excited state, may be accepted.

(I)

(II)

We have undertaken an extensive study of the ultraviolet spectra of sulphoxides with a view to obtaining information on the following points: (1) the mode of electronic excitation in the derivatives of methylphenyl sulphoxide, (2) the mode of electronic excitation in diphenyl sulphoxide and its derivatives, (3) the effect of bulky *ortho*-substituents on the sulphoxide conjugation, (4) the possibility of chelation occurring in *o*-hydroxy sulphoxides, and (5) the effect of solvent. The present paper deals with the effect of solvent. In Table I are recorded the spectral data for methyl-, ethyl-, propyl- and butyl-phenyl sulphoxides.

TABLE I
(Wave-lengths in mμ)

Sulphoxide.	<i>cyclohexane</i> .		Ethanol (95%).	
	λ_{max} .	ϵ_{max} .	λ_{max} .	ϵ_{max} .
Methylphenyl	253	4,000	237	4,100
Ethylphenyl	253	3,700	240	4,200
Propylphenyl	257	3,700	244	4,500
Butylphenyl	263	3,800	251	4,200

The absorption maximum occurs at a longer wave-length in *cyclohexane* (non-polar solvent) than in ethanol (polar solvent), the difference in wave-lengths being as much as 12–15 $m\mu$. This is rather interesting because the solvent effect on the absorption spectra of sulphones is negligible (Baliah and Shanmuganathan, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, **62**, 255). To emphasise the uniqueness of the sulphoxides in this respect, the spectral data for some alkylphenyl sulphides and alkylphenyl sulphones in hexane^a and ethanol are shown in Table II for comparison.

TABLE II
(Wave-lengths in $m\mu$)

Compound.	Hexane ^a .		Ethanol (95%).	
	λ_{max} .	ϵ_{max} .	λ_{max} .	ϵ_{max} .
Methylphenyl sulphide	255*	6,900	254	9,500
Ethylphenyl sulphide	256	7,200	256**	7,900
Propylphenyl sulphide	..	..	258**	5,600
Butylphenyl sulphide	268	1,300	215**	8,700
	219	11,400	218**	12,000
Methylphenyl sulphone	217*	7,000	217	6,700
Butylphenyl sulphone	213	8,400	216	8,700

^aIn *cyclohexane*.

Data from Fehnel and Carmack (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71, 84).

It is seen that the solvent effect is negligible for sulphides and sulphones. For ketones, considerable bathochromic shifts of absorption maxima occur on changing the solvent from *cyclohexane* to ethanol—just the reverse of what happens in the case of sulphoxides. An explanation was offered by Baliah and Shanmuganathan (*loc. cit.*) for the effect of solvent on the spectra of sulphones and ketones. The blue shift, which occurs for alkylphenyl sulphoxides on changing the solvent from *cyclohexane* to ethanol, indicates that the ground states are more stabilised in ethanol than in *cyclohexane* because it is not probable that their excited states are more stabilised in *cyclohexane* than in ethanol.

The greater stabilisation in ethanol cannot be merely due to hydrogen-bond formation, for then a similar behaviour should be observable in the case of sulphones also. A possible explanation for the greater stability of alkylphenyl sulphoxides in ethanol towards electronic excitation is that these are solvated in ethanol as follows :

There can be no objection to structure (III) because sulphur is known to utilise its vacant 4s- or 3d-orbitals (Fehnel and Carmack, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 231 ; Baliah *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1957, **61**, 1013 ; Baliah and Miss Uma, *Naturwiss.*, 1958, **45**, 512 ; Varadachari, Ph.D. thesis, Annamalai University, 1959). The solvent interaction postulated for sulphoxides is not possible for sulphides and sulphones.

In contrast to alkylphenyl sulphoxides, diaryl sulphoxides show a different solvent effect. The absorption maxima of diaryl sulphoxides occur at longer wave-lengths in ethanol than in *cyclohexane* (see Table III).

TABLE III
(Wave-lengths in m μ)

Sulphoxide.	<i>cyclohexane</i> .		Ethanol (95%).	
	λ_{max} .	ϵ_{max} .	λ_{max} .	ϵ_{max} .
Diphenyl	227	12,600	232.5	13,700
2-Methyldiphenyl	228*	11,800	235*	14,500
4-Methyldiphenyl	233*	11,200	238	16,500
2-Methoxydiphenyl	..	..	235	13,500
			285	4,100
4-Methoxydiphenyl	248	16,100	248	17,100
4-Nitrodiphenyl	261	11,100	265	11,100
4 : 4'-Dimethyldiphenyl	237*	15,800	240	19,000
4 : 4'-Dimethoxydiphenyl	..	..	251	23,000
2-Chlorodiphenyl	230*	13,500	235*	14,800
4-Chlorodiphenyl	234*	15,800	239*	18,200
4 : 4'-Dibromodiphenyl	248*	21,900	249	22,500

*Data from Leandri *et al.*, *loc. cit.*

The solvent effect on the spectra of diaryl sulphoxides indicates that the excited states of these compounds should be more stabilised in ethanol than in *cyclohexane*. This can be explained if the electronic excitation is supposed to occur in the following way :

The magnitude of the ionic charge is greater in the excited state and, hence, there will be greater stabilisation of the excited state in ethanol due to greater solvation. Then the following question naturally arises : why should not the kind of solvation postulated for the alkylphenyl sulphoxides in the ground state be postulated for the diaryl sulphoxides also ? The answer to this question seems to be that the diaryl sulphoxides are stabilised in the ground state to a greater extent than the alkylphenyl sulphoxides due to increased resonance resulting from the presence of two benzene nuclei. The resonance energy thus resulting should be greater than solvation energy that can result from solvation of the type postulated in the case of alkylphenyl sulphoxides.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the sulphoxides used in the present investigation, excepting the new ones specified below, were prepared as described in the literature.

Phenylpropyl Sulphoxide.—To a solution of phenylpropyl sulphide (5 g.) in acetic acid (80%, 75 c.c.) at 60° was added a saturated aqueous solution of chromic anhydride (2.4 g.). The mixture was heated for 20 mins. at 60–70°. After cooling it was poured on ice-water, extracted with ether, and dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate. After distilling off the ether, the sulphoxide boiled at 127°/7 mm, yield 2 g. (Found : C, 64.09 ; H, 7.34. C₉H₁₂OS requires C, 64.27 ; H, 7.19%).

Phenylbutyl sulphoxide was prepared by the oxidation of phenylbutyl sulphide (de la Mare and Vernon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 41) (4 g.) with hydrogen peroxide (30%, 7 c.c.) in the usual way. The yield was 2 g. The sulphoxide, after a number of recrystallisations from ethanol, melted at 58-59°. (Found: C, 65.73; H, 7.83. $C_{10}H_{14}OS$ requires C, 65.88; H, 7.74%.)

2-Methoxydiphenyl Sulphoxide.—2-Methoxydiphenyl sulphide (Mauthner, *Ber.*, 1906, 39, 3595) (2.7 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (25 c.c.) and mixed with an aqueous solution of chromic anhydride (0.9 g.). The mixture was heated for 20 mins. at 60-70°, cooled and poured on crushed ice. A solid gradually separated. It was removed by filtration. After four recrystallisations from ethanol it melted at 96-97°, yield 1 g. (Found: C, 67.33; H, 5.25. $C_{13}H_{12}O_2S$ requires C, 67.19; H, 5.21%.)

4-Methoxydiphenyl Sulphoxide.—4-Methoxydiphenyl sulphide (2.7 g.) was oxidised with an aqueous solution of chromic anhydride (0.9 g.) as described for the foregoing compound. The yield was 0.8 g. After a number of recrystallisations from methanol, the sulphoxide melted at 68-69°. (Found: C, 67.25; H, 5.71. $C_{13}H_{12}O_2S$ requires C, 67.19; H, 5.21%.)

Ultraviolet Absorption Measurements.—The ultraviolet absorption spectra were determined with a Beckman quartz spectrophotometer, model DU. Ethanol was purified by distillation after treatment with lead acetate and sodium hydroxide. cycloHexane was purified by distillation after passing repeatedly through a column of silica gel. Hexaneⁿ was purified by the method of Castille and Henri (*Bull. Soc. Chim. biol.*, 1924, 6, 299; *Chem. Abst.*, 1924, 18, 3165).

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